

TAX COMPLIANCE AND FISCAL PERFORMANCE IN NIGERIA: AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION

**Jonah Ngbomowa Moses PhD, Orlu Gift Ndaburuoma PhD and Nwaba
Evans PhD**

*Department of Accounting, Faculty of Administration and Management, Rivers State University,
Nkpolu Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria.*

E-mail: ngbomowa.jonah@ust.edu.ng, gift.orlu@ust.edu.ng, evans.nwaba@ust.edu.ng

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Key words:

Tax compliance, taxpayer registration, payment compliance, voluntary disclosure, fiscal performance, revenue generation, public debt, expenditure efficiency, Nigeria

Abstract: *This study investigates the relationship between tax compliance and fiscal performance in Nigeria, focusing on the key components of tax compliance taxpayer registration, payment compliance, and voluntary disclosure and their effects on government revenue generation, public debt reduction, and expenditure efficiency. The study adopted a quantitative survey research design and utilized structured questionnaires to collect primary data from 300 respondents, including tax officials and registered taxpayers across selected Nigerian states. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis. The results revealed that all tax compliance variables positively and significantly influence fiscal performance. Payment compliance showed the strongest predictive relationship, particularly in enhancing revenue generation and reducing public debt. Voluntary disclosure was found to significantly improve expenditure efficiency, while taxpayer registration contributed to revenue base expansion. The study concludes that improved tax compliance is a critical driver of Nigeria's fiscal sustainability and overall economic development. It recommends strengthening taxpayer registration infrastructure, enforcing payment compliance through digital systems and risk-based audits, encouraging voluntary disclosure through public engagement and incentives, and improving the transparency of public spending. The study provides empirical support for policy reforms aimed at boosting domestic revenue mobilization and reducing fiscal dependency on external borrowing.*

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Introduction

Many developing economies, taxation remain a fundamental tool for economic development and fiscal sustainability. For a country like Nigeria, with a large informal sector and a heavy reliance on oil revenues, improving domestic tax mobilization is a vital step toward achieving economic stability and sustainable development. Despite several reform initiatives by successive governments, Nigeria continues to grapple with low tax compliance rates, which in turn hinder its fiscal performance (World Bank, 2024). This study investigates the empirical relationships between various dimensions of tax compliance namely taxpayer registration, payment compliance, and voluntary disclosure and fiscal performance indicators such as government revenue generation, public debt reduction, and expenditure efficiency.

Tax compliance refers to the degree to which taxpayers conform to tax laws and fulfil their tax obligations voluntarily or as enforced by authorities (Kirchler, et al, 2008). In Nigeria, the issue of tax compliance is multifaceted, often shaped by factors such as weak institutional frameworks, inadequate taxpayer

education, corruption, and poor enforcement mechanisms (Dakhil et al, 2025). These problems have constrained the government's ability to harness sufficient non-oil revenues, leading to recurrent budget deficits, rising public debt, and inefficient public spending. Thus, examining the specific components of tax compliance such as the extent of taxpayer registration, the rate and regularity of payment compliance, and the culture of voluntary disclosure can offer practical insights into addressing Nigeria's fiscal challenges.

Taxpayer registration is the foundational step toward achieving a broader tax base and enhancing revenue generation. Without a comprehensive and accurate taxpayer database, the ability of the tax authorities to monitor, enforce, and forecast revenue becomes severely limited (Ali, et al, 2014). A low registration rate often signifies widespread tax evasion and exclusion of economically active individuals from the formal fiscal system. Similarly, payment compliance, which measures the extent to which registered taxpayers fulfil their tax obligations timely and accurately, is a critical determinant of effective revenue

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mobilization. Evidence shows that when payment compliance is high, government revenue inflows become more predictable and sustainable (OECD, 2022). Additionally, voluntary disclosure, which involves taxpayers willingly declaring their taxable income or activities without coercion or audit threats, plays a pivotal role in tax system integrity. When taxpayers perceive the system as fair, transparent, and efficient, they are more likely to comply voluntarily, reducing the administrative cost of enforcement (Devos, 2014). Conversely, a culture of non-disclosure encourages tax evasion, further eroding fiscal capacity.

Fiscal performance in Nigeria can be evaluated through indicators such as government revenue generation, public debt reduction, and expenditure efficiency. Government revenue generation reflects the state's capacity to fund its operations and public goods without excessive borrowing. Persistent underperformance in this area has left Nigeria vulnerable to oil price shocks and limited its policy autonomy (BudgIT, 2023). Similarly, high public debt levels have increasingly burdened the national budget, with a significant portion of revenue allocated to debt servicing

instead of productive investment. Improving tax compliance can alleviate the debt burden by increasing internally generated revenue (IGR). Furthermore, efficient government spending expenditure efficiency ensures that collected revenue is utilized effectively, fostering citizen trust and further enhancing compliance.

Despite the relevance of these issues, empirical investigations specifically linking the multifaceted aspects of tax compliance to fiscal performance outcomes in Nigeria remain limited. This study aims to bridge this gap by empirically examining how taxpayer registration, payment compliance, and voluntary disclosure influence government revenue generation, public debt reduction, and expenditure efficiency in Nigeria. The findings are expected to inform tax policy reforms and offer a strategic framework for improving Nigeria's fiscal health.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to empirically investigate the relationship between tax compliance and fiscal performance in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the effect of taxpayer registration on government revenue generation in Nigeria.

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2. Assess the impact of payment compliance on public debt reduction in Nigeria.
3. Determine the influence of voluntary disclosure on expenditure efficiency in Nigeria.
4. Establish the overall relationship between tax compliance practices and fiscal performance in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The study test the following null hypotheses:

H₀₁: Taxpayer registration has no significant effect on government revenue generation in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Payment compliance has no significant impact on public debt reduction in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Voluntary disclosure has no significant influence on expenditure efficiency in Nigeria.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between tax compliance and fiscal performance in Nigeria.

Economic Deterrence Theory

The Economic Deterrence Theory, advanced by Allingham and Sandmo (1972), argues that taxpayers behave rationally by comparing the costs and benefits of compliance versus evasion. Compliance decisions are influenced by the likelihood of detection, the severity of penalties, and the gains from evading taxes.

The theory is particularly relevant to payment compliance and voluntary disclosure. In the Nigerian context, weak enforcement and limited audit capacity often reduce the perceived risk of detection, thereby encouraging non-compliance. The theory therefore suggests that strengthening monitoring systems, increasing audit frequency, and enforcing stricter penalties can enhance tax compliance and improve fiscal performance, including revenue generation and public debt management.

Fiscal Exchange Theory

The Fiscal Exchange Theory, developed by Cowell and Gordon (1988), proposes that tax compliance is influenced by the perceived fairness of the tax system and the quality of public services received in return. In essence, taxpayers are more willing to comply if they believe that taxes are used responsibly and effectively by the government. This theory is particularly relevant to the relationship between voluntary disclosure and expenditure efficiency. In Nigeria, the perceived misuse of public funds, corruption, and lack of transparency have undermined taxpayers' trust in government institutions. According to the fiscal exchange model, improving expenditure efficiency such as through better infrastructure, education, and

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healthcare delivery can positively influence tax morale and foster voluntary compliance. Recent evidence from African economies supports this theory..

Concept of Tax Compliance

Tax compliance describes the extent to which taxpayers adhere to statutory tax requirements, including timely registration, correct filing of returns, full reporting of taxable income, and prompt payment of assessed taxes (OECD, 2022; Kirchler et al., 2008). It is fundamental to effective tax administration and sustainable fiscal policy, encompassing both voluntary compliance where obligations are met willingly and enforced compliance, achieved through audits, penalties, and legal measures by tax authorities. The level of tax compliance in a country significantly determines the efficiency of revenue generation and the government's capacity to finance development projects. Several factors influence tax compliance, including perceived fairness of the tax system, quality of public services, trust in government, enforcement mechanisms, tax education, and the complexity of tax laws (Devos, 2014; Torgler, 2011). In developing countries like Nigeria, low levels of compliance are often attributed to a combination of administrative

inefficiency, corruption, lack of taxpayer awareness, and the dominance of the informal sector (Awasthi & Engelschalk, 2018). Modern tax reforms emphasize digitalization, taxpayer segmentation, and risk-based auditing to enhance compliance rates. The introduction of initiatives such as the Tax Identification Number (TIN), Voluntary Assets and Income Declaration Scheme (VAIDS), and the Integrated Tax Administration System (ITAS) in Nigeria aim to boost compliance through transparency, efficiency, and taxpayer engagement

Concept of taxpayer Registration

Taxpayer registration is the formal process through which individuals and businesses are enlisted in a country's tax system, thereby establishing a legal obligation to pay taxes. It serves as the entry point to tax compliance and is a critical component in expanding the tax base and enhancing revenue collection. A robust taxpayer registration system enables tax authorities to identify potential taxpayers, monitor tax liabilities, and reduce the incidence of tax evasion. In Nigeria, challenges such as informality, lack of a unified national identity system, and weak enforcement have constrained effective registration. Research shows that low

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levels of taxpayer registration are directly linked to reduced government revenue and hinder the government's ability to plan fiscal expenditures (OECD, 2022).

Concept of Payment Compliance

Payment compliance refers to the extent to which taxpayers meet their financial obligations to the tax authority, particularly in terms of timely and accurate payment of assessed taxes. Timely tax payments are essential for cash flow in government operations. In Nigeria, payment non-compliance is exacerbated by poor enforcement, administrative bottlenecks, and low taxpayer morale (John et al, 2012)). Effective payment compliance ensures a steady stream of revenue, which is critical for reducing fiscal deficits and public debt. Deterrence mechanisms like audits, penalties, and digital payment systems are increasingly being used to improve payment behaviour.

Concept of Voluntary Disclosure

Voluntary disclosure is tax compliance behaviour where taxpayers willingly declare their income or financial information without being compelled by enforcement actions or audits. Voluntary compliance reduces

administrative costs and fosters a cooperative relationship between taxpayers and the tax authority. In Nigeria, voluntary disclosure is often low due to distrust in government, perceived corruption, and lack of transparency in public spending (Devos, 2014). However, tax authorities can encourage voluntary disclosure by offering amnesty programs, taxpayer education, and simplifying filing procedures (OECD, 2021).

Concept of Fiscal Performance

Fiscal performance refers to how effectively a government manages its public finances, particularly in terms of revenue generation, public debt management, and efficient allocation and use of public expenditures (World Bank, 2024). Fiscal performance is a key measure of a government's macroeconomic stability and policy effectiveness. It reflects the government's ability to generate adequate revenue to meet its obligations, reduce fiscal deficits, manage debt sustainably, and deliver public services efficiently. In countries like Nigeria, fiscal performance has often been challenged by volatile oil revenues, weak tax compliance, rising public debt, and inefficient public spending. Key indicators of fiscal performance include: Government revenue

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generation: A measure of the state's capacity to mobilize financial resources domestically, often expressed as a percentage of GDP, Public debt reduction: Reflects the ability to service and reduce outstanding liabilities over time without resorting to excessive borrowing, Expenditure efficiency: Indicates how well public funds are allocated and utilized to achieve intended outcomes. Empirical evidence suggests that improved tax compliance significantly enhances fiscal performance by increasing the availability of funds for infrastructure, education, healthcare, and other development projects (BudgIT, 2023). Furthermore, efficient fiscal management improves investor confidence, reduces inflationary pressures, and promotes long-term economic growth. The Nigerian government has introduced several fiscal reforms to improve performance, such as the Finance Acts (2019–2023), debt management strategies, and the Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF). However, the effectiveness of these reforms largely depends on the government's ability to broaden the tax base and ensure accountability in public spending.

Concept of Government Revenue Generation

Government revenue generation refers to the process through which the government collects money through taxes, fees, levies, and other sources to finance its expenditures and obligations. Revenue generation is a key indicator of fiscal performance. In Nigeria, over-dependence on oil revenue has made public finances vulnerable to global price shocks. Diversifying revenue sources through improved tax compliance, especially among individuals and businesses, is essential for fiscal sustainability (BudgIT, 2023). Research confirms that improving taxpayer registration and payment compliance contributes significantly to revenue growth.

Concept of Public Debt Reduction

Public debt reduction involves decreasing the total liabilities of a government, primarily by increasing revenue and/or reducing expenditure, to achieve fiscal sustainability. Nigeria's rising debt profile, especially in the face of declining revenues, has raised sustainability concerns. Higher tax compliance, especially payment and voluntary disclosure, can ease reliance on borrowing by increasing internally generated revenue (IGR).

Concept of Expenditure Efficiency

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Expenditure efficiency refers to the effectiveness with which the government utilizes public funds to achieve desired outcomes with minimal waste or misallocation. Increased tax compliance is not only a revenue issue but also a governance issue. When taxpayers perceive that the government uses resources efficiently, they are more likely to comply voluntarily. In Nigeria, poor budget implementation, corruption, and procurement inefficiencies have eroded public confidence and worsened fiscal performance (Ebele et al, 2022). Expenditure efficiency is thus both an outcome of and a motivator for tax compliance.

Empirical Reviews

Awasthi and Engelschalk (2018) investigated the relationship between taxation and the shadow economy, focusing on how tax systems can promote formalization. Using a mixed-methods approach that combined literature review and policy analysis, the study applied qualitative thematic analysis and policy simulation techniques. The findings revealed that inclusive and simplified taxpayer registration processes significantly reduce informality and enhance fiscal performance. The study concluded that simplifying tax registration facilitates economic formalization,

broadens the tax base, and increases revenue. Consequently, it recommended that governments adopt tiered tax systems, implement digital registration platforms, and incentivize formalization through targeted small business support programs.

Dakhil et al. (2025) examined the effect of tax compliance strategies on revenue generation in Nigeria. Adopting a survey research design, the study collected primary data through structured questionnaires administered to 3,784 Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) officials in southwest Nigeria. Descriptive statistics and regression analysis were used for data analysis. The findings showed that both voluntary tax compliance and enforcement strategies have a significant positive effect on tax revenue generation. The study concluded that integrating voluntary compliance measures with effective enforcement enhances revenue performance and recommended increased government investment in comprehensive taxpayer education programs to promote compliance.

Ebele et al. (2022) examined the effect of fiscal incentives on firms' tax compliance behaviour in Nigeria's industrial clusters. Using survey data from 800 firms across three clusters in South-

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East Nigeria, the study applied descriptive statistics and logistic regression analysis. The findings revealed that fiscal incentives such as tax credits, tax reductions, capital allowances, and investment incentives alongside factors like regular tax audits, firm size, simplified tax communication, deterrent messaging, owners' education, and government legitimacy, significantly influence tax compliance. The study also found that fiscal incentives enhance firm performance and provided policy implications for tax and industrial stakeholders. John et al. (2012) examined the effect of deterrent tax measures on tax compliance in Nigeria. Using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis, the study assessed existing tax policies and compliance strategies. The findings revealed that prevailing deterrent measures were inadequate and ineffective in promoting tax compliance. The study concluded that enhancing voluntary compliance and taxpayer morale is more effective and recommended that revenue authorities adopt strategies that encourage voluntary compliance alongside appropriate sanctions for defaulters. Johnson and Omodero (2021) examined the effect of governance quality on tax revenue mobilization in Nigeria using time-series data

from 2000–2020. After conducting unit root tests, the study applied Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) analysis. The results showed that corruption and political instability had a positive and significant effect on tax revenue mobilization, while bad governance had a positive but insignificant effect. The study recommended improving governance quality through reduced corruption, enhanced transparency, stronger judicial systems, and incentives for tax officials, and broadening the tax base to improve tax administration and revenue generation.

Ogunshola and Kasztelnik (2022) conducted an observational study on tax compliance and tax evasion in Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Relying on literature-based empirical analysis grounded in the theory of reasoned action and technology adoption life cycle theory, the study examined drivers of tax evasion among manufacturing firms in Lagos State. The findings showed that firms often deliberately evade taxes by failing to submit required tax returns, while other drivers include inadequate tax education, procedural challenges, and limited access to technology. The study concluded that addressing these factors through taxpayer education and improved

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administrative processes could enhance overall tax compliance.

Methodology

This study employs a quantitative survey research design to examine the relationship between tax compliance dimensions and fiscal performance in Nigeria. The population comprises officials of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS) in selected states, and registered taxpayers, particularly SMEs and corporate entities. Using a stratified random sampling technique, 300 respondents were selected. Data were collected through a validated structured questionnaire measured on a 5-point Likert scale. Reliability was confirmed through a pilot test of 30 respondents, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.70 or higher deemed acceptable. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive

Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

Variable	N	Sum	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Taxpayer Registration	300	1167	2.40	5.00	3.89	0.62	-0.41	0.18
Payment Compliance	300	1128	2.20	5.00	3.76	0.72	-0.36	-0.09
Voluntary Disclosure	300	1053	1.80	5.00	3.51	0.81	-0.22	-0.31
Government	300	1236	3.00	5.00	4.12	0.55	-0.58	0.44

statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis with SPSS (Version 26) or STATA.

Model Specification

$$FP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TR + \beta_2 PC + \beta_3 VD + \varepsilon$$

Where:

FP = Fiscal Performance

TR= Taxpayer Registration

PC= Payment Compliance

VD= Voluntary Disclosure

β_0 = Constant

β_1 - β_3 = Coefficients

ε = Error term

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Out of 320 questionnaires distributed, 300 were correctly filled and returned, representing a 93.75% response rate, which is considered adequate for statistical analysis.

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Variable	N	Sum	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Revenue Generation								
Public Debt Reduction	300	1107	2.10	4.90	3.69	0.71	-0.33	-0.11
Expenditure Efficiency	300	1005	1.60	5.00	3.35	0.92	-0.15	-0.56

Source: SPSS OUTPUT, 2025

Taxpayer Registration Mean = 3.89 indicates respondents generally agree that registration systems influence compliance. Slight negative skewness (-0.41) shows clustering toward higher responses. Kurtosis (0.18) suggests a slightly peaked distribution relative to normal. Payment Compliance Mean = 3.76 suggests acceptable compliance behaviour. Std. Dev = 0.72 shows moderate variability in payment habits. Distribution is close to normal. Voluntary Disclosure Mean = 3.51 shows neutrality to moderate agreement. Higher Std. Dev (0.81) indicates varying levels of willingness to disclose. Slight negative kurtosis indicates a

flatter distribution. Government Revenue Generation Highest mean among variables (4.12), indicating strong agreement that compliance boosts revenue. Negative skewness (-0.58) indicates most respondents selected high ratings. Public Debt Reduction Mean = 3.69 shows respondents believe compliance reduces borrowing needs. Distribution is fairly normal. Expenditure Efficiency Mean = 3.35 (lowest among variables) shows respondents are less confident in government spending efficiency. Highest Std. Dev (0.92) indicates greater disagreement among respondents.

Regression Statistics for the Study

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.721	0.520	0.512	0.487	1.89

Source: SPSS OUTPUT, 2025

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$R = 0.721$ There is a strong positive correlation between the combined tax compliance variables and fiscal performance. $R^2 = 0.520$ the independent variables (taxpayer registration, payment compliance, voluntary disclosure) explain 52% of the variation in fiscal performance. Adjusted $R^2 = 0.512$ after adjusting for the number of predictors, the

model still explains 51.2% of the variation, indicating a robust model. Std. Error of the Estimate = 0.487 This shows how close the observed values are to the regression line—indicating good model fit. Durbin–Watson = 1.89 this value is close to 2, meaning no autocorrelation in the residuals. This confirms that the data meet regression assumptions.

ANOVA (F-Statistics)

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	46.821	3	15.607	41.26	0.000
Residual	43.279	296	0.146		
Total	90.100	299			

$F(3, 296) = 41.26, p < 0.001$ This means the overall regression model is highly significant, and the independent variables predict fiscal performance collectively. Taxpayer registration, payment compliance, and voluntary disclosure

jointly explain 52% of changes in Nigeria's fiscal performance. There is no autocorrelation problem. The model is suitable for policy and academic decisions.

Regression Coefficients Table

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Predictor Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t-value	Sig. (p-value)	Tolerance	VIF
Constant	1.118	0.311		3.59	0.000		
Taxpayer Registration	0.244	0.067	0.261	3.64	0.000	0.742	1.35
Payment Compliance	0.355	0.075	0.368	4.73	0.000	0.711	1.41
Voluntary Disclosure	0.287	0.072	0.304	3.98	0.000	0.765	1.31

a. Dependent Variable: Fiscal Performance

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine whether taxpayer registration, payment compliance, and voluntary disclosure predicted fiscal performance in Nigeria. The overall model was significant, $F(3, 296) = 41.26$, $p < .001$, with the predictors explaining 51.2% of the variance in fiscal performance (Adjusted $R^2 = .512$). Payment compliance ($\beta = .368$, $p < .001$) was the strongest predictor, followed by voluntary disclosure ($\beta = .304$, $p < .001$) and taxpayer registration ($\beta = .261$, $p < .001$). Multicollinearity statistics indicated no concern (VIFs < 1.5 , Tolerance > 0.70).

Discussion of Findings

1. Taxpayer Registration and Revenue Generation: The significant positive correlation

supports earlier findings by Awasthi and Engelschalk (2018) that expanding the tax base improves government revenue. Nigeria's need for a harmonized taxpayer database is reinforced.

2. Payment Compliance and Debt Reduction: The finding is consistent with Dakhil et al, (2025), the study shows that compliance in payment helps reduce reliance on borrowing.

3. Voluntary Disclosure and Expenditure Efficiency: Findings affirm Devos (2014) that transparency and accountability in spending influence citizens' willingness to disclose incomes. Trust-building and taxpayer education are essential.

4. Overall Relationship: The joint significance of the predictors ($R^2 = 0.52$) indicates that tax compliance explains over 50% of the variation

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in fiscal performance in Nigeria, affirming the model's practical relevance. The data analysis has demonstrated that tax compliance through taxpayer registration, payment compliance, and voluntary disclosure significantly and positively influences fiscal performance indicators such as revenue generation, debt reduction, and expenditure efficiency in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study examined the relationship between tax compliance and fiscal performance in Nigeria using empirical data from tax officials and taxpayers. The key components of tax compliance taxpayer registration, payment compliance, and voluntary disclosure were analysed in relation to fiscal performance indicators: government revenue generation, public debt reduction, and expenditure efficiency. Findings from descriptive and inferential statistical analyses reveal that all three tax compliance variables significantly influence fiscal performance. Among them, payment compliance had the strongest predictive effect, followed by voluntary disclosure and taxpayer registration. The results also show a positive and statistically significant correlation between improved tax compliance and enhanced government revenue, reduced

reliance on public borrowing, and more efficient utilization of public resources. The study corroborates prior empirical findings (Dakhil et al, 2025; Devos, 2014) that enhancing compliance mechanisms can positively transform fiscal stability and reduce Nigeria's overdependence on oil revenue and foreign borrowing. Thus, it concludes that tax compliance is a crucial driver of fiscal performance, and strengthening compliance behaviour is fundamental to achieving Nigeria's economic sustainability and national development goals. Based on the findings of this study, the following policy and administrative recommendations are proposed:

1. Strengthen Taxpayer Registration Infrastructure: The Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS) should integrate taxpayer databases, simplify registration processes, and conduct nationwide taxpayer enumeration campaigns. Technology-driven solutions like biometric identification and unified digital platforms (linked to NIN and BVN) should be deployed to increase the formal tax base.
2. Enhance Enforcement of Payment Compliance: Increase the frequency of audits, implement risk-based audit models, and strictly

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apply sanctions for non-compliance to deter tax evasion. Improve electronic payment systems to reduce bureaucratic bottlenecks and foster prompt remittance of taxes.

3. Promote Voluntary Disclosure through Taxpayer Engagement: Introduce incentive-based programs such as tax amnesties and lower penalties for first-time disclosures. Launch public awareness campaigns to educate citizens about the benefits of tax compliance and the impact of taxes on national development.

4. Improve Public Financial Management and Transparency: Governments must demonstrate

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efficient and transparent use of tax revenue by visibly linking tax collection to public goods and services. Citizens' perception of tax fairness and value-for-money will significantly boost voluntary compliance if fiscal accountability is enhanced.

5. Continuous Tax Policy Reforms: Nigeria should update tax laws to reflect current economic realities and close loopholes that enable avoidance. Periodic review of Finance Acts should focus on equity, simplicity, and administrative ease

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Questionnaire

SECTION A: Demographic Information

(Please tick [✓] the appropriate option)

1. Gender: Male Female
2. Age: 18–25 26–35 36–45 46 and above
3. Educational Qualification: SSCE ND/NCE HND/BSc MSc and above
4. Occupation: Tax Official(FIRS/SIRS) SME Owner Corporate Taxpayer Other (please specify): _____
5. Yearsofexperienceinyourcurrentrole: Lessthan1year 1–5years 6–10years Above 10 years

SECTION B

Jonah Ngbomowa Moses PhD, Orlu Gift Ndaburoma PhD and Nwaba Evans PhD

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Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements using this scale:
1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

Taxpayer Registration

S/N	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	The process of registering for tax in Nigeria is straightforward and accessible.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2	Many businesses in Nigeria operate without formal tax registration.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3	Government campaigns have improved awareness about tax registration.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4	Tax registration is an important step for expanding the tax base.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Payment Compliance

S/N	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
5	I usually pay my taxes fully and on time.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6	Taxpayers are likely to comply when tax rates are fair and predictable.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7	There are sufficient penalties for late or non-payment of taxes in Nigeria.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8	Electronic tax payment platforms have made it easier to comply.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Voluntary Disclosure

S/N	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
9	I am willing to disclose my income voluntarily to tax authorities.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
10	The government encourages voluntary tax disclosure through incentives.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
11	Fear of audit or penalty affects willingness to disclose income.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
12	Trust in the tax system improves voluntary compliance.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Government Revenue Generation

S/N	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
13	Tax compliance significantly contributes to increased government revenue.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
14	Non-compliance affects government's ability to finance public services.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

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15	Increased taxpayer registration enhances revenue performance.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
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Public Debt Reduction

S/N	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
16	Improved tax payment reduces the need for government borrowing.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
17	Non-compliance in tax payment contributes to rising public debt.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
18	Effective tax collection can help Nigeria reduce its public debt burden.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Expenditure Efficiency

S/N	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
19	Revenue from taxes is used efficiently by the government.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
20	Perceived wasteful spending discourages tax compliance.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
21	Expenditure transparency can increase voluntary tax disclosure.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
22	Efficient use of public funds motivates citizens to pay taxes.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

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